

Quantum Spin, Constraints, Degeneracy and Matrices

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 26, 2021

In classical physics, angular momentum is defined by $\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{p}$ (\mathbf{r} , \mathbf{p} vectors) which is constrained motion because it is angular momentum. There is also the idea of degeneracy present because for a fixed angular momentum, say a classical object orbiting another in a circle, the magnitude of velocity is the same at each point.

In classical electrodynamics, one may consider the case of a photon, i.e. Maxwell's equations without source or current terms. These lead to \mathbf{E} (electric) and \mathbf{B} magnetic fields existing in a plane perpendicular to the photon motion (and to each other). In addition, one may take the four equations and obtain a wave equation for both \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} . Given a wave equation, one has a degeneracy in the direction of \mathbf{E} . Alternatively, one may create a circularly polarized \mathbf{E} which has a constant magnitude, but moves in a circle like angular momentum which it is. In fact, this circularly polarized motion represents spin 1, but is seen as classical motion.

To make a link with quantum mechanics, one may take the two classical Maxwell's equations: $d\mathbf{E}/dt = \text{grad} \times \mathbf{B}$ and $d\mathbf{B}/dt = -\text{grad} \times \mathbf{E}$ and write them in terms of a matrix equation (with the matrix coming from i times the Levi-Civita symbol) i.e. $id/dt (\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B}) = (\mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{p}) (\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B})$ ((1)) where $\mathbf{p} = -i \text{grad}$ and $\mathbf{S} = i \mathbf{e}_{ijk}$ and \mathbf{e}_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol. The consequence of using a matrix is that it has eigenfunctions which may be related to a constraint i.e. there may be a fixed "angular momentum" i.e. spin and one finds projection eigenfunctions. This occurs for ((1)) which is a matrix equation (containing spin) created from purely classical equations. The eigenvalues of the particular matrix are discrete (i.e. there is quantization) and one may form a linear combination to find the most general math solution which is the opposite of what one would do in classical physics. For example, for a spin one object, an m projection of 1 means angular motion in one direction while -1 is in the opposite direction. In classical physics, where one can track a particle at each point at each time, one physically distinguishes between clockwise and counterclockwise motion. In quantum mechanics, one does not distinguish states at a point, but globally and so both clockwise and counterclockwise states may exist in a wavefunction, but it may collapse to one or the other when a measurement occurs.

We examine the behaviour of matrices, constraints and degeneracies in the photon wavefunction created from Maxwell's classical electromagnetism equations, because we wish to extend these ideas to the Dirac electron. In general, physics texts speak of linearizing the Klein-Gordon wave equation. What happens during this linearization is that matrices appear which follow constraint equations. There have eigenfunctions and eigenvalues which we argue is the pattern for angular motion i.e. spin. The type of matrix which appears governs the spin present and again one adds eigenfunctions for the most general solution in quantum mechanics. This is completely opposite of classical physics, but explains the Stern-Gerlach experiment. Thus, we argue that matrices which appear (constrained) when one linearizes a quadratic differential equation linking energy and momentum in quantum mechanics points to degenerate (because it does not appear in the \mathbf{p} , \mathbf{E} equation explicitly), constrained motion i.e. angular motion or spin.

Classical Angular Momentum

Classical angular momentum is given by $\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{p}$ (\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{p} vectors, \mathbf{p} =momentum). To maximize angular momentum, \mathbf{p} should be perpendicular to \mathbf{r} . In other words, angular momentum is a kind of constrained motion. Furthermore, one may have the magnitudes of \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{p} be constant which yields degeneracy i.e. the same value of angular momentum at each point in a circle for example. This degeneracy appears again for the case of polarized E and B fields in a photon.

Maxwell's Equations and the Photon

In the 1800s long before quantum mechanical considerations, Maxwell developed his electromagnetic equations based on a variety of experimental results. He found that if one eliminated sources and currents one had:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{E}}{dt} = \text{grad} \times \mathbf{B} \quad \frac{d\mathbf{B}}{dt} = -\text{grad} \times \mathbf{E} \quad \text{grad} \cdot \mathbf{E} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{grad} \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad ((1))$$

The last two equations show that \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} lie in a plane perpendicular to the motion of the photon i.e. \mathbf{k} if $\exp(i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{x} - i\mathbf{E}t)$ is a solution to a wave equation which may be formed from ((1)). In other words, one may find a wave equation with solutions:

$$\mathbf{E} = \cos(\omega(t - z/c)) \langle \mathbf{n} \rangle \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where } \langle \mathbf{n} \rangle \text{ is a unit vector in a certain direction in a plane perpendicular to the photon motion. } \mathbf{B} \text{ is a vector in the same plane perpendicular to } \mathbf{E}.$$

A degeneracy arises immediately because $\langle \mathbf{n} \rangle$ may point in any direction in the plane. One may consider a fixed length \mathbf{E} i.e.:

$$\mathbf{E} = \cos(\omega(t - z/c)) \langle \mathbf{x} \rangle + \sin(\omega(t - z/c)) \langle \mathbf{y} \rangle \quad \text{where } \langle \mathbf{x} \rangle \text{ and } \langle \mathbf{y} \rangle \text{ are perpendicular unit vectors in the plane.}$$

The magnitude of \mathbf{E} is constant, but its direction moves in a circle. This is called circular polarization and we argue that it is constrained motion following by adding motion to the degeneracy in ((2)). In other words, it represents constant angular motion or spin because $\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B})$ is energy density, but at this point it is completely classical. Classical means one may distinguish \mathbf{E} at each x, y point in the plane at each instant of time. In other words, the \mathbf{E} vector is either moving clockwise or counterclockwise, but not both.

It is possible to take the first two Maxwell's equations for a photon in ((1)) and write a matrix equation. One may ask what is the objective of writing an equation using a matrix. A matrix may have discrete eigenvalues and eigenfunctions. It may be associated with a constant angular momentum or spin with the eigenvalues describing projections - in other words it may be associated with constrained motion.

It is interesting that Maxwell's classical equations allow one to write an equation with matrices which is the first step to introducing quantum spin associated with a photon. (The wave features

i.e. frequency and wavelength already follow from the wave equation which is created by the four equations in ((1)) which are all classical.)

The first two equations of ((1)), written in terms of $EI + iB$ yield:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} [EI + iB] = \text{grad} \times (iB + EI) \quad \text{or} \quad i \frac{d}{dt} [EI + iB] (i) = -i \epsilon_{ijk} dj (iE-B) (k)$$

$$= i \epsilon_{ijk} dj (iE-B) (k) = -i [S \cdot p] (EI+iB) (i) \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where } dj = d/dx_j, \epsilon_{ijk} \text{ is the Levi-Civita symbol and } p = -i \text{ grad}$$

Here the i th spin matrix is: $i \epsilon_i(jk)$.

It may be noted that ((2)) is a completely classical equation, but introducing a matrix means one may find eigenfunction/ eigenvalue solutions. The eigenvalues are 1,0 and -1 which are quantized i.e. one already thinks in quantum terms. 1 and -1 represent clockwise and counterclockwise motion, but because one deals with eigenfunctions, a general solution may mix -1 with 1 (and also 0). Thus, one may have both clockwise and counterclockwise motion together which is completely unclassical. We argue that it is unclassical because in quantum mechanics one may not follow a particle at each point at each time and so one may not discern locally whether there is angular momentum in a clockwise or counterclockwise direction. This discernment must occur globally and so the most general solution at any point consists of all three eigenfunctions (with weights).

The spin matrices S_x, S_y and S_z are related to axes, but are linked to an overall spin or angular momentum with eigenvalues of $s(s+1)$ where s is the overall spin. (These ideas follow from the quantum theory of angular momentum which is developed independently of spin.)

The above argument started with the ideas of degeneracy and constrained motion which were then linked to a matrix related to angular motion or spin. Our next goal is to see if these ideas pertain to the Dirac equation for a free particle.

Dirac Equation for a Free Particle

The Dirac equation for a free particle follows from linearizing the quadratic Klein-Gordon equation which links energy, rest mass and momentum. This process mathematically requires the use of matrices which follow constraints. We ask whether one should anticipate that angular momentum i.e. spin should follow from such a scenario. We try to argue that it should, based on the ideas related to the photon case. Matrices have eigenfunctions and eigenvalues representing projections of a fixed spin or angular momentum. The type of matrix determines the overall spin. There is a degeneracy because this angular motion (spin) does not overtly affect the relationship between energy, rest mass and momentum. It is a basic property of the particle. (If it contributes energy, this may be part of the rest mass.)

We argue that it is not a surprise that Dirac's matrix solution appears similar to Pauli's earlier solution with Pauli matrices. (Dirac's scenario, however, follows directly from the Klein Gordon case and also describes anti-particles.)

We argue that the presence of matrices with their constraints is linked to angular momentum or spin. There is also the idea of degeneracy present because one has the projections (1,0) and (0,1) i.e. this is not the spin 1 case of the photon, but a spin $\frac{1}{2}$ case.

Matrix eigenvalues are discrete indicating quantization and one again takes linear combinations in order to obtain the most general solution because one cannot follow motion at any given point so one does not know if one has spin up or down, it is a global property. A wavefunction, however, may be in one or the other state or a linear combination of both as shown in the Stern Gerlach experiment.

There is also degeneracy as (1,0) and (0,1) (from s_z) states have the same energy for a free particle with no B field present. The Pauli matrices which are part of 4x4 matrices of Dirac are linked to coordinates x,y,z, but are associated with a fixed spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that angular momentum is due to constrained motion and linked to degeneracy. E.g. a particle may move in a circle with each point having the same radius and the same velocity magnitude. Furthermore, the velocity vector is constrained to be perpendicular to the radius. One may find this degeneracy at work in Maxwell's classical solution for a photon. The electric E and magnetic B fields are perpendicular and lie in a plane perpendicular to the photon motion, but one does not know the orientation of the E vector i.e. there is degeneracy. One may take a set of degenerate E directions which have the same energy and form circularly polarized light. This yields a fixed angular momentum, but does not change the energy i.e. spin is not a factor when considering an equation linking energy to momentum. One may also take the first two Maxwell equations from ((1)) and form a matrix equation. These matrices S_x , S_y , S_z are linked to constant angular motion or spin of 1. Eigenvalues are discrete which represent quantization and one may take linear combinations of eigenfunctions which violates classical physics which may distinguish any kind of motion at each point Quantum mechanics cannot. One has orthonormal eigenfunctions because they are distinguished globally.

We apply these ideas to Dirac's equation and argue that the presence of constrained matrices which follow from the linearization of the Klein-Gordon equation are the consequence of constrained motion with degeneracies because the spinor does not change the energy of the free particle in the absence of a B field. Thus, the emergence of constrained matrices when linearizing a quantum equation linking energy and momentum, may be a signature of constrained, degenerate motion i.e. angular motion or spin (which has this property). The type of matrix determines the spin.